

MONIMED - Monitoring Mediterranean climate-smart forestry practices for climate resilience and ecosystem service provision

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Deliverable 2.1. **Description of the applied CSF practices**

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Abstract

This deliverable gives an in deep description of the forest management practices implemented in the project and of the previous conventional practices applied in the same areas. The objective is to characterise the initial conditions of the forest stands where the treatments will be or were implemented, as the basis to monitor the changes in the following years.

The first section is a short introduction to the deliverable. The second section describes the forest management activity in Requesens, with a description of the initial conditions of the forest, the conventional practices applied in 2015, and the new practices applied in 2025. The third section reproduce the same information from the Montesquiú field trail and the fourth section for the Montnegre-Corredor trail.

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1. Introduction

Rural abandonment in recent decades, combined with climate change, has rendered Euro-Mediterranean Forest areas highly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change, thereby threatening the provision of ecosystem services. Historically, forest management in Mediterranean regions was characterised by high intensity, system simplification, and a single-product focus. Contemporary forest structures are the outcome of these historical trends, leading to management abandonment in highly vulnerable stands prone to drought, pest outbreaks, and wildfires.

Over the past decades, several demonstrative projects have assessed the impact of forest management on the adaptive capacity of Mediterranean forests. These studies have focused on monitoring key indicators such as forest growth, tree vitality, and fire risk reduction following different thinning intensities and understory clearing treatments. **This project seeks to advance adaptive forest management by integrating closer-to-nature management strategies and incorporating novel parameters** related to multifunctional management, biodiversity conservation, carbon sequestration potential, and climate resilience. The project encompasses the long-term monitoring of ongoing pilot sites under conventional management (10 and 5 years of monitoring) alongside newly established adjacent pilots implementing Climate-Smart Forestry (CSF) practices: (1) integrative multifunctional management and (2) management geared towards fostering natural development processes. All management approaches will be assessed using newly defined indicators reflecting the forest's capacity to support biodiversity, its carbon sequestration potential, and its resilience to climatic stressors.

This report gives an in deep **description of the forest management practices** implemented in the project and of the previous conventional practices applied in the same areas. The objective is to **characterise the initial conditions of the forest stands** where the treatments are implemented, as the **basis to monitor the changes** in the following years.

The project is developed in the **Mediterranean area of Catalonia** (NE Spain), taking advantage of the existing network of CREAM pilots on adaptive forest management, including the most representative Mediterranean forest types (dominated by *Quercus ilex*, *Quercus humilis* and *Pinus sylvestris*). The field trials are established in three sites:

- A Holm oak forest in La Albera protected area (Girona).
- A mixed forest of *Pinus sylvestris* and oaks in the Montesquiú natural park (Barcelona).
- A Holm oak forest in the Montnegre-Corredor natural park (Barcelona).

2. Holm oak forest in La Albera protected area (Girona)

The Holm oak (*Quercus ilex*) is one of the most representative evergreen oaks in the Mediterranean. The selection of the location in La Albera protected area responded to the high vulnerability of the area to climate change impacts, being a highly fire-prone forest remaining unmanaged for the last 80 years. The surrounding area experienced a 2012 wildfire, and a sudden change in wind direction was the only reason that this area was not burned.

2.1. Initial characteristics of the Holm oak forest

Holm oak is the dominant species (80-90% of the basal area), accompanied by several other species, including cork oak (*Quercus suber*), downy oak (*Quercus pubescens*), *Phillyrea angustifolia*, and *Erica arborea*, among others. An initial inventory determined that this forest is highly dense (over 2,500 trees/ha, diameter at breast height higher than 7.5 cm), with a basal area of 31.5 m²/ha and an irregular structure. According to the estate owners, the forest has remained unmanaged for approximately 80 years. Figure 1 shows the initial characteristics of the forest.

Figure 1. Initial characteristics of the Holm oak forest in Requesens.

2.2. Conventional silvicultural practices

In 2015, as part of the LIFE MEDACC project (LIFE12 ENV/ES/000536, <http://medacc-life.eu/>), two conventional silvicultural practices were applied in the site. The treatments had the main objective to **reduce the fire risk and water stress** through the reduction of tree density and the promotion of mature structures with bigger trees and fuel discontinuity. The practices were designed together with local stakeholders and the ownership, particularly with the public body in charge of forest management (Forest Ownership Centre, CPF), and with the Forest Science and Technology Centre of Catalonia (CTFC) according to the adaptive management guidelines compiled in ORGEST (Vericat, et al., 2011).

In this site, three plots of about 1 ha were implemented in 2015:

- Plot of **low intensity treatment**: Application of a low thinning clearing with the objective to adapt the forest to a regular structure. Regular forests are, in general, more efficient in the water use and in fire prevention. The intensity of the practice was:
 - A 10%-reduction in basal area and a 18%-reduction in density, primarily affecting smaller diameter. The low thinning operation impacted 2-3 sprouts per stump.
 - No changes in the canopy cover to prevent resprouting.
- Plot of **high intensity treatment**: Application of a selection treatment and intense understory clearing to adapt forest to an irregular structure and to stimulate forest regeneration. Irregular forests are supposed to preserve better the soil, its quality and nutrients. The intensity of the practice was:
 - A 33%-reduction in basal area and 43%-reduction in density.
 - A 40%-reduction of canopy cover, to stimulate resprouting.
- **Control plot**, with no intervention.

Table 1 summarizes the initial density and basal area of each treatment area, the same numbers after the implementation of the forest management in 2015, and the percentage of change. Figure 2 and Figure 3 shows the final estate of the Holm oak forest after the two treatments.

Table 1. Summary of the density and basal area per treatment, before the forest management, after the management and percentage of change.

Treatment	Density			Basal area		
	Pre-treatment (ft/ha)	Post-treatment (ft/ha)	Change (%)	Pre-treatment (m ² /ha)	Post-treatment (m ² /ha)	Change (%)
Control	2,164.5	2,164.5	-	32.8	32.8	-
Low intensity	2,811.7	2,291.8	18%	28.1	25.4	10%
High intensity	2,599.5	1,485.4	43%	33.5	22.5	33%
Mean value	2,525.3	1,980.6		31.5	26.9	

Figure 2. Estate of the Holm oak forest after the low intensity treatment.

Figure 3. Estate of the Holm oak forest after the high intensity treatment.

2.3. New Climate-Smart Forestry practices

The existing silvicultural practices were supplemented with two additional field trials within the framework of the MONIMED project. Two new 1-hectare plots were established in the field, where CSF practices were implemented between January and February 2025:

- **Close-to-Nature Silviculture Plot:** This silvicultural approach involves applying targeted treatments to enhance tree species diversity, promote mixed stand structures and functional diversity, and regulate competition while simultaneously supporting the vitality of dominant trees, stimulating fruit production, and mitigating water competition.

In this plot, an individual-tree silvicultural method has been employed, prioritizing the selection of high-quality trees for multiple objectives (biodiversity conservation, timber production, and natural regeneration). Specific silvicultural interventions have been applied to optimize their development, including reducing direct competition.

Site-specific factors such as soil characteristics, light availability, and species composition have guided the applied treatments. This method aims to balance sustainable yield with biodiversity conservation while maintaining key ecosystem functions.

At this stage of the project, treatment intensity has not yet been quantified. However, the plots will be reassessed at the project's conclusion to enable precise characterization of the applied interventions.

- **Plot of preparation to natural dynamics** in non-productive stands: This intervention aims to promote forest maturity and restore complex ecological processes by minimizing human influence. The following actions were implemented:
 - Increasing coarse woody debris stocks both on the forest floor (through tree felling) and standing (via tree girdling).
 - Enhancing the vitality and dimensions of larger-diameter trees by alleviating direct competition, thereby contributing to biodiversity conservation and structural maturity.
 - Promoting vertical heterogeneity by creating small canopy openings within the forest.

Figure 4 and Figure 5 shows the final estate of the Holm oak forest after the new CSF practices.

Figure 4. Estate of the Holm oak forest after the closer-to-nature silviculture.

Figure 5. Estate of the Holm oak forest after the preparation to natural dynamics.

Figure 6 shows the location and shape of the four treatment plots and the control plot in Requesens.

Figure 6. Location of the treatment plots (red polygons) in Requesens.

2.4. Cost of the practices

The total costs of the practices are included in Table 2. The costs need to be referenced to the year when actions were implemented to make comparisons.

Table 2. Implementation costs of the practices.

Treatment	Implementation costs (€/ha)	Year of execution
Low intensity treatment (T2)	1,600 €/ha	2015
High intensity treatment (T1)	2,000 €/ha	2015
Closer-to-nature treatment (T3)	1,250 €/ha	2025
Preparation to natural dynamics (T4)	500 €/ha	2025

The forest treatments have produced different products that are sold to obtain benefits, as included in Table 3.

Table 3. Benefits of the obtained products.

Treatment	Firewood / biomass		Total benefits €	Benefits €/ha	Year of execution
	tones	€/tone			
Low and High intensity treatment (T1-T2) ¹	12.0	60.0	720 €	360 €/ha	2015
Closer-to-nature treatment (T3)	-	-	-	-	2025
Preparation to natural dynamics (T4)	-	-	-	-	2025

¹ The products obtained in 2015 are cumulative for all treatment areas, and the results are not differentiated by treatment.

3. Mixed forest of *Pinus sylvestris* and oaks in the Montesquiú natural park (Barcelona)

Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) is an evergreen coniferous with a wide range of distribution across Europe, the Iberian Peninsula being the Southern limit of its distribution. The selection of the location in Montesquiú natural park responded to the high vulnerability of the area to climate change impacts. In recent years, an increasing number of studies have reported forest declines and shifts in species composition in Scots pine forests in the Mediterranean region as a response to changing climatic conditions. The selected area had suffered last decade tree decline episodes and plagues, which park managers attribute to episodes of drought as the main cause.

3.1. Initial characteristics of the mixed forest

The mixed forest of *Pinus sylvestris* and *Quercus humilis* is in Montesquiú natural park (Barcelona). Scots pine is the dominant species in the area (68% of the basal area), accompanied by several other species, including *Quercus pubescens*, maple (*Acer monspessulanum*), *Crataegus monogyna* and *Buxus sempervirens*, among others. An initial inventory determined that this forest is a moderately dense forest (more than 1,000 ft/ha), with a basal area of 24.2 m²/ha of pine and 8.7 m²/ha of the escort species, a regular structure and a 65% canopy cover. According to the park managers, the forest has not been managed for the last 40 years (approximately). Figure 7 shows the initial characteristics of the forest.

Figure 7. Initial characteristics of the mixed forest in Montesquiú.

3.2. Conventional silvicultural practices

In 2015, as part of the LIFE MEDACC project (LIFE12 ENV/ES/000536, <http://medacc-life.eu/>), two conventional silvicultural practices were applied in the site. The treatments had the main objective to **improve the tree health containing tree mortality, and also**

to evaluate the potential of oak replacement of Scots pine under conditions of climate change. The practices were designed together with local stakeholders, particularly with Park managers (Diputació de Barcelona).

In this site, four plots of about 1 ha were implemented in 2015:

- Plot of **low intensity treatment**: Application of understory clearing with the objective to reduce resources competition. The intensity of the practice was:
 - A 26%-reduction in basal area and a 44%-reduction in density of the escort species, without any effect on Scots pine. Considering all species, a 4%-reduction in basal area and a 17%-reduction in density.
- Plot of **high intensity treatment**: Application of low thinning and intense understory clearing with the objective to reduce tree competition. Elimination of escort species and dominated Scots pines
 - A 17%-reduction in basal area of Scots pine and a 17%-reduction of escort species. A 25%-reduction in density of Scots pine and a 22%-reduction of escort species. Considering all species, a 17%-reduction in basal area and a 24%-reduction in density.
- **Plot of pine logging**. Elimination of Scots pines to accelerate the replacement of pines by oaks and evaluate the oaks' future development.
 - A 100%-reduction in basal area of Scots pine and a 30%-reduction of escort species. A 100%-reduction in density of Scots pine and a 35%-reduction of escort species. Considering all species, a 75%-reduction in basal area and a 64%-reduction in density.
- **Control plot**, with no intervention.

Table 4 summarizes the initial density and basal area of each treatment area and each species group (differentiating between Scots pine and the accompanying species), the same numbers after the implementation of the forest management in 2015, and the percentage of change. Figure 8, Figure 9 and Figure 10 shows the final estate of the mixed forest in Montesquiú after the three treatments.

Table 4. Summary of the density and basal area per treatment, before the forest management, after the management and percentage of change.

Treatment	Density								
	Scots pine			Other species			Total		
	Pre-treatment (ft/ha)	Post-treatment (ft/ha)	Change (%)	Pre-treatment (ft/ha)	Post-treatment (ft/ha)	Change (%)	Pre-treatment (ft/ha)	Post-treatment (ft/ha)	Change (%)
Control	509.3	509.3	-	551.7	551.7	-	1,061.0	1061.0	
Low intensity	583.6	583.6	0%	360.8	201.6	44%	944.3	785.2	17%
High intensity	647.2	488.1	25%	477.5	371.4	22%	1,124.7	859.4	24%
Pine substitution	838.2	0.0	100%	1,061.0	689.7	35%	1,899.2	689.7	64%
Mean value	644.6	357.2		612.7	453.6		1257.3	848.8	

Treatment	Basal area								
	Scots pine			Other species			Total		
	Pre-treatment (m ² /ha)	Post-treatment (m ² /ha)	Change (%)	Pre-treatment (m ² /ha)	Post-treatment (m ² /ha)	Change (%)	Pre-treatment (m ² /ha)	Post-treatment (m ² /ha)	Change (%)
Control	18.3	18.3	-	10.6	10.6	-	29.0	29.0	
Low intensity	23.9	23.9	0%	4.8	3.5	26%	28.7	27.4	4%
High intensity	28.1	23.2	17%	4.8	3.9	17%	32.9	27.2	17%
Pine substitution	26.4	0.0	100%	14.5	10.2	30%	40.9	10.2	75%
Mean value	24.2	16.4		8.7	7.1		32.9	23.4	

Figure 8. Estate of the mixed forest after the low intensity treatment.

Figure 9. Estate of the mixed forest after the high intensity treatment.

Figure 10. Estate of the mixed forest after the pine substitution treatment.

3.3. New Climate-Smart Forestry practices

The existing practices were complemented with two more field trials in the framework of the MONIMED project. Two new plots of 1 hectare were defined in the field, where CSF practices were implemented along December 2024 and January 2025:

- **Close-to-Nature Silviculture Plot:** The same treatment as Requesens forest was applied.
- **Plot of preparation to natural dynamics** in non-productive stands: The same treatment as in Requesens forest was applied.
- **Control plot 2:** A newly designated non-intervention area was established to serve as a reference for comparing the two new CSF practices with an unmanaged site. This additional control area was necessary because Control Plot 1 exhibits significantly different forest structure and age, making it unsuitable for direct comparison with the newly defined areas.

Figure 11 and Figure 12 shows the final estate of the mixed forest after the new CSF practices.

Figure 11. Estate of the mixed forest after the closer-to-nature silviculture.

Figure 12. Estate of the mixed forest after the preparation to natural dynamics.

Figure 13 shows the location and shape of the four treatment plots and the control plot in Montesquiú.

Figure 13. Location of the treatment plots (red polygons) in Montesquiú.

3.4. Cost of the practices

The total costs of the practices are included in Table 5. The costs need to be referenced to the year when actions were implemented to make comparisons.

Table 5. Implementation costs of the practices.

Treatment	Implementation costs (€/ha)	Year of execution
Low intensity treatment (T1)	1,920 €/ha	2015
High intensity treatment (T2)	3,620 €/ha ²	2015
Pine substitution treatment (T3)	2,800 €/ha	2015
Closer-to-nature treatment (T4)	1.268 €/ha	2025
Preparation to natural dynamics (T5)	500 €/ha	2025

² The costs/ha in treatment 2 in Montesquiú is higher than expected due to was necessary to open two extraction lines to pull out the wood.

The forest treatments have produced different products that are sold to obtain benefits, as included in Table 6.

Table 6. Benefits of the obtained products.

Treatment	Firewood / biomass		Wood		Paper wood		Total benefits €	Benefits €/ha	Year of execution
	tones	€/tone	tones	€/tone	tones	€/tone			
Low and High intensity treatment (T1-T2) and pine substitution (T3) ³	11.2	28	43.2	38	21.4	20	2,383.2 €	794.4 €/ha	2015
Closer-to-nature treatment (T3)			17.0	70	3.7	45	1,356.6 €	1,356.6 €/ha	2025
Preparation to natural dynamics (T4)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2025

³ The products obtained in 2015 are cumulative for all treatment areas, and the results are not differentiated by treatment.

4. Holm oak forest in the Montnegre-Corredor natural park (Barcelona)

The Holm oak (*Quercus ilex*) is one of the most representative evergreen oaks in the Mediterranean. The selection of the location in Montnegre-Corredor natural park responded to the high vulnerability of the area to pests, forest fires and droughts.

The Montnegre-Corredor area as a whole and specifically the pilot study area has been significantly affected by **pests**. On the one hand, the pine forests are in a state of general decline due to the interaction of various factors, such as the orography, forest management of the area, repeated episodes of drought, etc. This decline triggered a serious infestation of the *Tomicus destruens* bark beetle in stone pines (*Pinus pinea*) from 2015 to 2018, leading to the death of many of them. Maritime pine has also been affected by the sucking insect *Matsococcus feytaudii*, which weakens it and increases its vulnerability to bark beetles.

In terms of **fire prevention**, the massif is part of the priority firebreak area, B3 Serra del Montnegre i el Corredor. Moreover, the specific area where the actions were implemented is a key fire prevention zone: it is within a Priority Management Area (AGP), more specifically in a Strategic Management Point (PEG in its Catalan acronym), meaning, in a zone where fuel modification and/or infrastructure preparation allows the fire service to carry out safe attack manoeuvres that reduce the spread of large forest fires.

4.1. Initial characteristics of the Holm oak forest

The Holm oak (*Quercus ilex*) forest is in Montnegre-Corredor natural park (Barcelona), in the private estate of Can Bordoï, that has remained untouched for the past 20 years. The forest is made up of a holm oak grove scattered with cork oak and small patches of stone pine and an undergrowth of tree heather and strawberry trees. The presence of holm oak varies and is distributed in patches, with some that are denser and others that have more tree heather and strawberry trees. The initial forest showed a **high fraction of canopy cover (CC of 84 %), high density (1,122 ft/ha) and basal area (25.3 m²/ha)** (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Initial characteristics of the Holm oak forest in Montnegre-Corridor.

4.2. Conventional silvicultural practices

In 2020, as part of the Interreg Sudoe MONTCLIMA project (<https://www.montclima.eu/en>), a conventional silvicultural practice was applied in the site. The treatment had the main objective to **reduce the forest stand's vulnerability to fire** based on improving its resistance and resilience to disturbances, increasing the complexity of its structure and composition. The practices were designed together with the Association of Forest Owners of the Montnegre-Corredor, in charge of the forest management of the Can Bordoï ownership.

The applied silviculture followed an irregular forest management model, involving gentle but frequent thinning was applied. This model considered that the application of a treatment is necessary when a basal area of at least 25 m²/ha is reached, which typically occurs in the massif every 10 years (rotation period) (Guitart, et al., 2022). Therefore, the silvicultural treatments implemented consisted of the following actions:

1. **Thinning:** gentle felling in patches of holm oak and the densest patches of stone pine, according to the following criteria: Selection of the healthiest and most robust trees of all ages; promotion of secondary or accompanying species, favouring biodiversity; fostering of the vertical discontinuity between strata through the extraction of trees; favouring of a homogeneous distribution and seed-bearing trees; ensuring the presence of regenerated areas and abundant stands of younger types of trees across the entire area; maintaining the remaining basal area equal to or greater than 20 m²/ha and a maximum reduction of 25 %; and maintaining a high residual CC (70-80%).
2. **Coppice management:** focused on younger oak trees to reduce competition among resources, concentrating growth in the trees that are best developed and positioned. Between 1 and 3 sprouts were selected per stump.
3. **Selective clearing:** reduction of shrub-level competition with tree regeneration, to favour certain shrub species that have value for the biodiversity and modify the vertical

and horizontal structure of the fuel layers to reduce vulnerability to fires. This involves a partial elimination of the shrub layer, considering the following criteria: scrub CC < 30 %; height < 1.3 m; coppice method applied to tree-like shrubs, such as tree heather and strawberry trees, maintaining the best developed and best positioned (1-3 sprouts/stump); and removal of flammable species and promotion of species that provide protection and/or food for fauna.

With this framework, two plots were implemented in 2020:

- Plot with an **irregular forest management model** (5.4 ha): In terms of forest structure, these treatments have led to:
 - A 14%-reduction in canopy cover, 19%-reduction in density and 8%-reduction in basal area.
 - A 77%-reduction scrub cover and a 97%-reduction in fuel biovolume.
- **Control plot** (1.9 ha), with no intervention.

Table 7 summarizes the initial density and basal area of each treatment area, the same numbers after the implementation of the forest management in 2020, and the percentage of change. Figure 15 shows the final estate of the Holm oak forest after the treatment.

Table 7. Summary of the density and basal area per treatment, before the forest management, after the management and percentage of change.

Treatment	Density			Basal area		
	Pre-treatment (ft/ha)	Post-treatment (ft/ha)	Change (%)	Pre-treatment (m ² /ha)	Post-treatment (m ² /ha)	Change (%)
Control	1199.0	1199.0		29.0	29.0	
Treatment	1075.0	872.0	19%	23.1	21.4	8%
Mean value	1137.0	1035.5		26.1	25.2	

Figure 15. Estate of the Holm oak forest after the treatment.

4.3. New Climate-Smart Forestry practices

The existing practices were complemented with two more field trials in the framework of the MONIMED project. Two new plots of 1 hectare were defined in the field, where CSF practices were implemented along December 2024 and January 2025:

- **Close-to-Nature Silviculture Plot:** The same treatment as Requesens forest was applied.
- **Plot of preparation to natural dynamics** in non-productive stands: The same treatment as in Requesens forest was applied.

Figure 16 and Figure 17 shows the final estate of the Holm oak forest after the new CSF practices.

Figure 16. Estate of the Holm oak forest after the closer-to-nature silviculture.

Figure 17. Estate of the Holm oak forest after the preparation to natural dynamics.

Figure 18 shows the location and shape of the four treatment plots and the control plot in Montnegre-Corredor.

Figure 18. Location of the treatment plots (red polygons) in Montnegre-Corredor.

4.4. Cost of the practices

The total costs of the practices are included in Table 8. The costs need to be referenced to the year when actions were implemented to make comparisons.

Table 8. Implementation costs of the practices.

Treatment	Implementation costs (€/ha)	Year of execution
Irregular model treatment (T1)	1,573.1 €/ha	2020
Closer-to-nature treatment (T2)	3,590.3 €/ha ⁴	2025
Preparation to natural dynamics (T3)	577.6 €/ha	2025

The forest treatments have produced different products that are sold to obtain benefits, as included in Table 9.

Table 9. Benefits of the obtained products.

Treatment	Firewood / biomass		Paper wood		Total benefits €	Transport costs €	Benefits €/ha	Year of execution
	tones	€/tone	tones	€/tone				
Irregular model treatment (T1)	61.9	66.6	-	-	4,126.92 €	1,055.0 €	568.9 €/ha	2020
Closer-to-nature treatment (T2)	31.23	65.0	5.66	30.0	2,199.8 €	-	2,199.8 €/ha	2025
Preparation to natural dynamics (T3)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2025

⁴ This cost includes project supervision and tree marking.

5. References

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